

ROLE OF JUDICIARY IN THE PREVENTION OF WOMEN TRAFFICKING IN INDIA

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Abstract

The Indian Constitution specifically bans the traffic in persons. Article 23, in the Fundamental Rights section of the constitution, prohibits 'traffic in human beings and other similar forms of forced labour.' Though there is no concrete definition of trafficking, it could be said that trafficking necessarily involves movement/transportation of a person by means of coercion or deceit and consequent exploitation leading to commercialization. The abusers, including the traffickers, the recruiters, the transporters, the sellers, the buyers, the end-users, etc., exploit the vulnerability of the trafficked person. Trafficking shows a phenomenal increase with globalization. Increasing profit with little or no risk, organized activities, low priority in law enforcement, etc., aggravate the situation. The income generated by trafficking is comparable to the money generated through trafficking in arms and drugs. Women are also trafficked into commercial markets to serve as labourers or domestic servants. Kuwait is considered a major centre of women trafficked for commercial exploitation, which, like those sent into prostitution, join recruiters who promise money and a better life. Their passports and immigration papers are frequently seized by their new owners once they reach Kuwait, leaving them completely vulnerable and without legal recourse.

Though Kuwait, according to investigations by the United States State Department, is one of the worst centres for trafficking in women, it is far from the only one. As of 2009, 17 countries were listed as Tier 3 by the US State Department, meaning that not only do they suffer high amounts of human trafficking, but also that the government does not meet minimum standards for eliminating the trade. The present study is a critical analysis of women trafficking in India.

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Keywords : Fundamental Rights, Commercial Markets, Forced Labour, Commercialization, and Minimum Standards for Eliminating the Trade.

Introduction

The crime or practice of illegally obtaining and relocating children, usually for forced labour or sexual exploitation, is child trafficking. In legal terms, human trafficking is the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or receipt of persons, using:

- Threats and force or other forms of coercion;
- Abduction;
- Fraud and deception;

The abuse of power or abuse of position of vulnerability and the awarding or receiving of compensation or benefits in order to maintain power over another person for the purpose of abuse. It is an internationally organized phenomenon clearly indicating human rights abuse. Due to persistent inequalities worldwide, women are more vulnerable to this slavery-like practice. This is a result of gender inequality prevailing in the form of violence. The offenders, including traffickers, recruiters, transporters, dealers, consumers, end-users, etc., are manipulating the vulnerability of the trafficked individual. Child and women trafficking are the gravest forms of abuse and exploitation of human beings. More than thousands of Indians are being trafficked every day to some destination or the other and are laboured to lead lives of slavery. They survive in brothels, factories, guesthouses, dance bars, and even in the homes of well-off Indians, with no control over their bodies and lives.

Definitions of Women Trafficking

Trafficking in persons is a serious crime and a grave violation of human rights. Every year, thousands of men, women, and children fall into the hands of traffickers, in their own countries and abroad. Almost every country in the world is affected by trafficking, whether as a country of origin, transit, or destination for victims. Article 3, paragraph (a) of the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons defines “trafficking in persons” as the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring, or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability, or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation.

Reason for Women Trafficking

Women are trafficked for both sexual-based and non-sexual-based exploitation. Sex-based trafficking includes prostitution, pornography, cybersex, exotic dancing, stripping, live sex shows, mail-order businesses, military prostitution, sexual tourism (debt bondage), massage parlours, beer bars, and strip clubs. While non-sexual-based trafficking could be for different types of servitude like domestic and agricultural labour, industrial labour, adoption, organ transplant, camel racing, marriage-related rackets, petty crimes, drugs, etc. but the growing trafficking in women is generally for the purpose of prostitution.

Where are they taken?

In addition to red light areas, women and children endure sex trafficking in hotels, vehicles, huts and private residences, religious pilgrimage centers, and the tourism industry (working for the foreigners as pleasure girls). Traffickers use websites, mobile applications, and banking systems for money transfers to facilitate commercial sex.

Women Trafficking in India

India is also a destination for women and girls from Nepal and Bangladesh trafficked for the purpose of commercial sexual exploitation. Nepali children are also trafficked to India for forced labour in circus shows. Indian women are trafficked to the Middle East for commercial sexual exploitation. Indian migrants who migrate willingly every year to the Middle East and Europe for work as domestic servants and low-skilled labourers may also end up part of the human-trafficking industry. In such cases, workers may have been recruited by way of fraudulent recruitment practices that lead them directly into situations of forced labour, including debt bondage; in other cases, high debts incurred to pay recruitment fees leave them vulnerable to exploitation by unscrupulous employers in the destination countries, where some are subjected to conditions of involuntary servitude, including non-payment of wages, restrictions on movement, unlawful withholding of passports, and physical or sexual abuse. In a recent survey in India, prostituted women cited the following reasons for their remaining in the trade, reasons that have been echoed in all concerned countries. In descending order of significance, they are poverty and unemployment; lack of proper reintegration services; lack of options; stigma and adverse social attitudes; family expectations and pressure; and resignation and acclimatization to the lifestyle. The two principal Indian laws that address trafficking and prostitution in particular are:

- The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act of 1986 (ITPA), colloquially called PITA, an amendment to SITA and
- The Suppression of Immoral Traffic in Women and Girls Act of 1956 (SITA).

Neither law prohibits prostitution per se, but both forbid commercialized vice and soliciting. Aside from lack of enforcement, SITA is problematic in several ways. One of its drawbacks is that the prescribed penalties discriminate on the basis of sex: a prostitute, defined under SITA as always a woman, who is arrested for soliciting under SITA could be imprisoned for up to a year, but a pimp faces only three months. SITA allowed prosecution of persons other than the prostitutes only if the persons involved “knowingly” or “willingly” made women engage in prostitution.

Accordingly, pimps, brothel owners, madams, and procurers could feign ignorance of prostitution and escape punishment. The client, moreover, was not viewed as an offender and could not be sanctioned under SITA. Finally, SITA only addressed street prostitution; prostitution behind closed doors was left alone, a loophole that actually promoted the establishment of brothels.

Role of Judiciary to prevent women trafficking

The judiciary plays a crucial role in preventing women trafficking by ensuring that laws are interpreted and applied effectively, protecting victims, and holding traffickers accountable. This includes raising awareness among judicial officers, providing victim support, and ensuring speedy court processes. The roles of the judiciary in preventing women trafficking and the interpretation and application of laws are such that the judiciary interprets and applies laws related to trafficking, ensuring that they are understood and implemented correctly, says a paper from Noida International University. The judiciary can order protective measures for victims, such as witness protection, to ensure their safety and well-being during legal proceedings. The judiciary holds traffickers accountable for their crimes, ensuring that they are punished according to the law. The judiciary can raise awareness about trafficking issues through judicial colloquiums and other training programs, says the Ministry of External Affairs. Speedy court processes of the judiciary can ensure that trafficking cases are processed and decided efficiently, providing victims with access to justice in a timely manner. The judiciary can contribute to developing bench books and best practices to reinforce victim-centre approaches in trafficking cases. The law is the tool of justice. The methods used to obtain justice are both objective under the law of the land and subjective under the circumstances of the crime or offense. In a metaphor, the accused and victim are represented as the two sides of a coin, and the law of the state is the deciding factor that must be considered in order to fairly adjudicate the case. A fundamental right that ensures everyone has access to justice is the protection of the law. It is necessary for the rule of law. Even the state is not exempt from the rule of law. It should be possible for everyone to seek the protection of the law and legal remedies for their complaints. Justice is the preservation of objectivity, equity, and righteousness. As old as the notion of politics is the theory of justice.

Indian Cases

M. H. Hoskotv/s. State of Maharashtra¹- In this instance, a special leave petition was filed to challenge the three-year term for cheating that the High Court had imposed. The court addressed two concerns, lenient sentencing in economic offenses and the ability to appeal, which it felt resulted from the facts of the case while dismissing the special leave petition. The court ruled that there is a constitutional right to legal help while discussing the latter. The trial court and appellate levels should provide free legal representation whenever a person's life or personal freedom is in jeopardy, the court concluded. The court will therefore, if the facts of the case, the seriousness of the punishment, and the interests of justices or enquire, assign competent counsel for the prisoner's defence provided the party does not object to the lawyer. This rule applies when a prisoner is

¹AIR1978SCC 1548

prevented from hiring a lawyer due to factors like indigence or being incommunicado. The state is responsible for funding these services.

Rajoo @ Ramakant v/s. State of Madhya Pradesh²-

The appellant was found guilty of gang rape and given a 10-year jail sentence. He did not have counsel throughout his appeal before the High Court. The entitlement to legal counsel during the appellate process is the main topic of discussion. The court noted that there is no distinction in the Legal Services Authority Act 1987 or the Constitution of India 1950 between a trial and an appeal for the purposes of providing free legal aid to an accused or a person in custody. The court recounted the legislative and judicial history of the right to legal aid. A qualified person has the right to legal representation at any point in the proceedings that he or she is either bringing or defending. Because of this, the High Court was bound to ask the man if he needed legal counsel and, if so, to pay for it. The court expressed concern in dictum regarding the exceptions to the right to legal representation for economic crimes, prostitution, and child abuse discussed in **Khatri and Others v/s. State of Bihar and Others³** and **Suk Das v/s. Union Territory of Arunachal Pradesh⁴** contending that these are not tenable in light of the constitutional mandate and the presumption of innocence principle. This was an appeal against a two-year sentence for criminal intimidation where the defendant had no legal representation throughout the trial and declined to request legal assistance. In this instance, the issue was whether denying him access to free legal aid would violate his fundamental right to legal representation at the expense of the state. The magistrate has a duty to advise the accused of his entitlement to free legal services if he cannot afford to hire an attorney due to poverty, the court reaffirmed in this case. In this instance, the trial was tainted by the violation of the accused's fundamental rights under Article 21 because the Additional Deputy Commissioner failed to inform the appellant of his right to free legal assistance, and the accused went unrepresented throughout the trial, which resulted in a conviction. As a result, the conviction was overturned.

Hari Singh v/s. Sukhbir Singh⁵-

The Supreme Court in this case recognized a different tendency, holding that the court's ability to award compensation under section 357 was not supplemental to her punishments but rather independent of them. Also, the court in this instance has expanded the definition of the clause to mean that the compensation should be appropriate and must be granted after taking into account both the accuser's financial capacity and the seriousness or malfeasance of the offense.

²(2012)8SCC553

³1981 CRI.L.J. 470

⁴AIR 1986 SC 991

⁵(1988)4SCC551

Delhi Working Women's Forum v/s. Union of India⁶-

In this decision, the Supreme Court stressed the establishment of a Compensation Board (reserved solely for rape victims). It commanded the National Commission for Women to develop a plan “so as to wipe the tears from the sad rape victims’ eyes.” In 1995, NCW forwarded a draft to the Central Government. The program is known as the “Scheme for Relief and Rehabilitation of Victims of Rape,” and some of its most notable features include the central government’s allocation of funds to the ministry of women and child development, the establishment of a Criminal Injuries Relief and Rehabilitation Board in each district, the determination of relief based on factors like the seriousness of the physical harm, the loss of income, the psychological trauma caused, and the provision of enhanced relief in grievous offenses.

Ankush Shiwaji Gaikwad v/s. The State of Maharashtra⁷-

The legislative goal of the measures relating to victim compensation, it was determined, was to reassure the victim that he is not an overlooked party in the criminal justice system.

Suresh v/s. State of Haryana⁸-

The state was ordered to pay a sum of Rs.10 lakhs to the family of the victims who had been kidnapped and killed, and the court granted the victim interim compensation.

Nilabati Behera v/s. State of Orissa⁹-

The Hon’ble Supreme Court has ordered the payment of monetary compensation as well as rehabilitative settlements in a number of cases where the state or other authorities failed to preserve the victims’ life, dignity, and liberty in order to do justice to the victims.

Manish Jalan v/s. State of Karnataka¹⁰-

The Supreme Court stated that the amount of compensation must be established by taking into account the type of crime committed, the harm sustained, and the defendant’s financial ability to make up the difference. Yet, the amount of the payment should be fair.

Nipun Saxena v/s. Union of India¹¹-

The National Legal Service Authority (NALSA) was ordered by the Supreme Court to create a program for victims of sexual offenses, including those covered under the Protection of Children against Sexual Offenses Act, after taking into account the shortcomings of existing programs (POCSO).

S.S. Ahluwalia v/s. Union of India¹²-

⁶1995SCC(1)14

⁷(1988)4SCC551

⁸Cri.ANo.420of2012

⁹(1993) 2 S.C.R. 581

¹⁰(2008)8SCC225

¹¹WP(C)No.565/2012

The Supreme Court decided that the government should compensate the families of those who were murdered in the riot in principle.

Hussainara Khatoun v/s. Home Secretary, State of Bihar¹³-

The rights of prisoners awaiting trial and the management of Bihar's jails were the subject of this PIL. Lastly, it made the government realize how important it is to launch a comprehensive legal services program.

Sheela Barse v/s. State of Maharashtra¹⁴-

In response to the abuse of female convicts in Bombay, a public interest lawsuit was brought. The court ordered the Maharashtra prisons to send a list of all under trial inmates to the district's legal aid committee and to facilitate interactions between attorneys recommended by these committees and inmates who need legal representation. This was done to guarantee that prisoners have access to legal aid.

Smt. Haimanti Mal v/s. The State of West Bengal¹⁵-

In this case, the issue of trauma brought on by physical abuse was addressed and compensated for in the absence of any medical findings. The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act of 2005's Section 22 served as the legal foundation for the Calcutta High Court's award of a compensation of one lakh rupees for mental torture and emotional suffering.

Rudal Sah v/s. State of Bihar,¹⁶-

in this case, the most well-known instance, Rudal Sah was imprisoned for 14 years despite being declared legally insane, and the Supreme Court of India ordered the state to pay him Rs. 35,000/- in compensation, ruling that Bihar had violated Article 21.

Nani Gopal Paul v/s. State Of West Bengal,¹⁷-

Laws prohibiting trades in noxious or dangerous goods or trafficking in women cannot be held to be illegal as enacting a prohibition and not a mere regulation. The Supreme Court repeated the same view in

Narendra Kumar and others v/s. The Union of India and Others¹⁸ on 3 December, 1959. It is not necessary for me, in this rule, to be concerned with this exception because the law I have to deal with is not the type of law that falls within the exceptions; I have merely noticed one possible exception to the generality of the observations.

¹²WP(C)No. 232/1997

¹³1979 AIR1369

¹⁴AIR1983SC 378

¹⁵C.R.R. No.3907/2016

¹⁶(1983) 4 SCC141

¹⁷AIR 1966 CAL 167

¹⁸1960 AIR 430

Vishal Jeet v/s. Union of India and Others on 2 May, 1990¹⁹- The Supreme Court recognized the severe issue of trafficking, particularly of women and children for prostitution. It emphasized the need for a multi-faceted approach involving prevention, rescue, and rehabilitation. The court also highlighted the socio-economic factors contributing to trafficking. This Public Interest Litigation (PIL) addressed the issue of child prostitution. The Supreme Court recognized the vulnerability of children from impoverished backgrounds and issued several directions to state governments and union territories. These included taking speedy action against child prostitution, establishing rehabilitative homes, and forming advisory committees to suggest measures for eradication and victim care.

Gaurav Jain v/s. Union of India²⁰ on 9 July, 1997, this case dealt with the rehabilitation of children rescued from brothels. While the case primarily focused on children, the underlying principles of dignity, the right to a healthy life, and the State's responsibility towards vulnerable individuals are equally applicable to adult women trafficked for sexual exploitation.

Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. Union of India and Others²¹ in WP (C) No. 51/2006, The Supreme Court recognized trafficking as an organized crime and defined it in accordance with the Optional Protocol of the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC). The court also ordered a total ban on the use of children in circuses.

Society of private unaided schools v/s. Union of India and Bachpan Bachao Andolan,²²- The apex court upheld the constitutional validity of the Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009.

Save the Child Foundation v/s. Union of India,²³ on 05.11.2014. The Court defined the roles and responsibilities of all government agencies in relation to a complete ban on child labour and also directed 500 children to be rescued every month, that charge sheets should be filed within 45 days in cases involving child labour and trafficking, and that the appropriate DLSAs should provide compensation to victims of trafficking.

Apne Aap Women Worldwide Trust India & Others v/s. The State of Bihar & Others²⁴- decided on 20 November, 2014: In this case the Patna High Court emphasized the need to tackle the menace of trafficking effectively, aligning with international conventions like the Palermo Protocol. The court stressed the importance of rescue, rehabilitation, and preventing re-trafficking of victims.

¹⁹1990 AIR 1412

²⁰(1997) 8 SCC 114

²¹(2011) 5 SCC 1

²²AIR 2012 SC 3445

²³WP (Cri.) 2069/2005

²⁴Civil Writ Case No. 1882/2013

Prajwala v/s. Union of India on 9 December, 2015,²⁵- The Supreme Court directed the Ministry of Home Affairs to establish an Organized Crime Investigative Agency (OCIA) to specifically address sex trafficking. While the agency's formation has faced delays, this case demonstrates the judiciary's concern and proactive approach towards combating organized trafficking networks. The court has repeatedly emphasized the need for comprehensive legislation and effective implementation to tackle this issue. Overruled on 12 November, 2024 in the same case²⁶ the Ministry of Home Affairs would set up the “Organized Crime Investigative Agency” (OCIA) to take care of the victims of sex trafficking.

Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. Union of India and Others,²⁷ W. P. (Civil) No. 906 of 2014 on 14 December, 2016. The Supreme Court directed the Union government to complete a national survey on substance abuse and formulate a comprehensive national plan.

Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. Union of India and Others,²⁸ on 5 September, 2017,²⁹ A PIL on missing children filled by BBA led to the ordering of mandatory registration of FIRs. Besides, the court ordered. The State of Commission for Protection of Child Rights (SCPCR) will monitor the standard operating procedure on missing children. The court also ordered the state commissions to use technology in the best interest of children.

State of Uttarakhand and v/s. Sartaj Khan on 7 December, 2017, this case highlights the role of law enforcement agencies in actively checking and preventing human trafficking, especially in vulnerable border areas. It underscores the state's duty to protect citizens from this crime.

In the case of **Chandra Prakash Kewal Chand Jain v/s. State of Maharashtra,**³⁰ the Supreme Court expressed its sentiments as follows: “Unfortunately, there is a decline in the regard for womanhood in our nation.” The current global standard of decency and morality in public life is also present in our country. Therefore, if the judiciary rigorously prosecutes individuals who violate societal norms, decency, and morality in public life, they can be safeguarded and promoted.

In the case of **Ram Narayan Gupta v/s. Ramaswami Gupta,**³¹- rendered a significant inference was made that acts of domestic violence are frequently perpetrated in fits of rage motivated by sexual envy. The mistreatment and frequent abuse of women demonstrate a profound and extreme antipathy towards social sentiments. Since the day of our independence, both the Indian legislature and the judiciary have endeavored to enhance the status of women. The judiciary

²⁵W.P. (C) No. 56/2004

²⁶Misc. Appl. No. 530/2022 in W.P. (C) No. 56/2004

²⁷AIR 2017 SC 754

²⁸WP (Cri.) No. 75/2012

²⁹Govt. Appeal No. 139/2016

³⁰AIR 1990 SC 658

³¹AIR 1988 SC 2268

construed the diverse legal provisions intended to safeguard women in a manner that maximized the advantages for our female population. The Indian Constitution ensures equality for all women in India through Article 14. The aforementioned provisions safeguard the dignity of women under Article 51(A) (e), prohibit state discrimination as outlined in Article 15.1, ensure equality of opportunity and pay for equal work as stipulated in Article 16, and provide maternity relief and provisions for securing humane working conditions and maternity leave for women as outlined in Article 42.³² The Supreme Court stated in the seminal case **Randhir Singh v/s. Union of India**³³ that while the principle of equal employment does not constitute a fundamental right, it is undeniably a constitutional objective. According to Article 39 (d) of the Constitution, “equal pay for equal work is guaranteed to men and women.” In a similar vein, the court ruled in **Grihakalyan v/s. Union of India**³⁴ that a classification that denies equal pay for equal labor constitutes an irrational classification as defined in Article 14.

The Court ruled in **Air India v/s. Nargesh Meerza & Others**³⁵ on 28 August, 1981 highlighting the invalidity and arbitrary nature of the service rules established by Indian Airlines and Air India. These rules mandated that air hostesses retire from service at the earlier of 35 years of age or upon marriage, or if they married within four years of confirmation or upon their first pregnancy, whichever occurred first, and that a pregnancy-based termination of service was capricious and arbitrary and thus in violation of Article 14.

In the context of **Vishaka & Ors v/s. State of Rajasthan & Others** on 13 August, 1997,³⁶ in pursuit of gender equality, the petitioner, a non-governmental organization (NGO) affiliated with the State of Rajasthan, Vishoka, initiated a writ petition to obtain the recognition of the fundamental rights of working women as enshrined in Article 21 of the Indian constitution. The petition was promptly filed in response to the 1992 gang rape of a Saathin from Rajasthan, who was employed in women's development programs as a social worker. As a retaliatory action, the assault occurred after the Saathin intervened to avert a child marriage. A seminal ruling was rendered by the Supreme Court of India concerning sexual harassment directed at women.

The Supreme Court of India, in the case of **Cehat and others v/s. Union of India**,³⁷ oversaw the implementation of the Prenatal Diagnostic Techniques Act and released useful directives. The matter of gender choice and sex-selective abortion was prominently featured in this petition,

³²IJCRT2403788.pdf

³³AIR 1982 SC 879

³⁴(1991) 1 SCC 619

³⁵AIR 1981 SC 1829

³⁶AIR 1997 SC 3011

³⁷(2003) 8 SCC 412

prompting numerous initiatives from governmental and non-governmental organizations to address this concern.

In **R. Ruppayee v/s. Raja Gounde**,³⁸ a case involving gift-related property, the Supreme Court ruled that a father may bequeath to his daughter ancestral immovable property within reasonable boundaries. Regarding the widow's claim to property, the Supreme Court ruled in the **Kalawatibai v/s. Soiryabai and Others** on 1 May, 1991³⁹ case that a female Hindu who owned the property as of the effective date of Section 14 of the Hindu Succession Act of 1956 could only acquire absolute ownership if she were a limited owner. The legislature did not intend to grant the benefit of estate enlargement to every female Hindu, regardless of her status as a limited proprietor.

It was noted in the case of **S. Lalitha Sundari and Another v/s. Thiru. R. Kethar Nathan and 3 others**⁴⁰ on 31 July, 2001 that the female descendants of the trustees were required to fill two positions on the Education Committee of a family trust. The appointing authority, the scheme court, appointed two male members and noted that the female candidates who participated in the interview lacked practical experience and were male descendants as well.

In India several judgments by the Supreme Court of India have been pivotal in addressing child trafficking as **Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. State of Punjab and Others**,⁴¹ the court directed the Punjab government to formulate an action plan and SOP for rescuing child laborers. **Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. Union of India Others**⁴² on 18 April, 2011, in this significant case, the Supreme Court recognized trafficking as an organized crime, aligning its definition with the Optional Protocol of the UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime. This recognition was crucial for framing stricter laws and approaches to combat trafficking.

Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. State of Jharkhand & Others⁴³ on 17 December, 2013, in response to this PIL, the court directed the constitution of the State Commission for Protection of Child Rights, State Child Protection Committees, CWCs, children's homes, and shelter homes, besides ordering the implementation of the Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection) Act.

Bachpan Bachao Andolan v/s. Union of India and Others,⁴⁴ on 06.09.2019. This PIL, related to a POCSO case, the Delhi High Court ordered the release of part of the Victim Compensation Fund that would not be less than Rs. 25 crores to the District Legal Services Authority.

³⁸AIR 2004 SC 1284

³⁹1991 AIR 1581

⁴⁰AIR2002MAD17

⁴¹WP (C) No. 7565/2010

⁴²AIR 2011 SC 3361

⁴³W.P. (PIL) No. 139 of 2011

⁴⁴W.P. (C) 466/2016

Pinki v/s. State of Uttar Pradesh on 15 April, 2025⁴⁵ a recent case in the Hon'ble Supreme Court has been actively pushing for the swift resolution of child trafficking cases. In this case, the court directed all High Courts to ensure that trials related to child trafficking are completed within six months and to report the progress. The court also highlighted concerns about low conviction rates due to factors like easy bail for traffickers, hostile witnesses, and delays in trials.

Conclusion

The Indian government is to enact comprehensive legislation that will tackle human trafficking and its fundamental problems. However, the government was supposed to adopt a broader perspective towards trafficking in accordance with Expert Committee recommendations. Ensuring effective legislation and its implementation will take time and patience, but considering Modi's government has a clear majority in Parliament and that the Women and Child Development Ministry is fully devoted towards fighting this menace, it is hoped that any new bill will bring all stakeholders on board to enact people centre social legislation that addresses some of the problems identified here and is in line with the expert committee recommendations. Thus, it may be concluded using the words of Justice V.R. Krishna Iyer, without prejudice to any one gender, "No nation, with all its boasts and all its hopes, can ever morally be clean till all its women are really free to live without the sale of their young flesh to lascivious wealth or the commercializing of their luscious figures.

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